

THE ROLE OF 4K SKILLS IN FORMING PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE

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Abstract: This article discusses the role and importance of 4K skills in the formation of pedagogical culture, as well as a special scientific approach to ensuring the harmony of critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration skills in the process of students' professional self-awareness.

Keywords: career choice culture, 4K skills, critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration, professional self-awareness, pedagogical model, competency-based approach.

Introduction. In the conditions of modern globalization, the sharply changing demands of the labor market require a new approach to the process of choosing a profession for young people. Today, not only the possession of specific knowledge and skills, but also the ability of a person to think independently, solve problems, work effectively in a team and freely express their ideas is of great importance. In this regard, the development of 4K skills in the education system - critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration - is considered one of the priority tasks. These skills have a direct impact not only on the general development of students, but also on the formation of a conscious and informed culture of choosing a profession.

An analysis of the scientific literature shows that the issues of career guidance and the formation of a culture of choosing a profession have been studied by many researchers. However, a comprehensive pedagogical model aimed at developing a culture of choosing a profession by integrating 4K skills has not been sufficiently developed. In particular, the issue of ensuring the harmony of critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration skills in the process of students' professional self-awareness requires a special scientific approach.

Analysis of the literature on the topic. The theoretical foundations of career choice and career guidance have been extensively studied by foreign and domestic scientists. In particular, the gradual formation of the process of professional development and career choice is explained in connection with the individual characteristics of the individual. In these approaches, career choice is interpreted as the result of a person's self-awareness, identification of interests and abilities, and interaction with the social environment. Also, in modern studies, the process of career choice is considered on the basis of a competency approach, in which special attention is paid to such aspects of the individual as independent decision-making, flexibility and social activity.

4K skills (critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration) are widely recognized internationally as the key competencies of 21st century education. The development of these skills serves to form students' abilities to solve complex problems, put forward new ideas, communicate effectively and work in a team. According to scientific sources, it is these skills that are an important factor in students' professional self-awareness and

conscious planning of their future activities. At the same time, it is emphasized that 4K skills should be formed in the educational process not only as separate competencies, but also as an integrated system.

Local studies have also studied the issues of guiding students to a profession, identifying their professional interests, and providing psychological and pedagogical support. At the same time, more traditional approaches prevail in existing scientific works, and the need to develop an integrative system based on a modern competency model, in particular, 4K skills, remains.

The above analysis shows that although the issue of forming a culture of career choice has been widely studied, its research as a complex, systematic and integrated pedagogical model based on 4K skills has not been sufficiently carried out. Therefore, this study is aimed at filling this gap and serves to develop effective pedagogical mechanisms for developing a culture of career choice in young people.

Research methodology. This study is aimed at developing an integrative pedagogical model based on 4K skills (critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration) in the formation of a culture of career choice in young people and determining its effectiveness, in which a system of complex methodological approaches was used.

The methodological basis of the study is the systematic, competency-based, person-oriented and activity-oriented approaches. Through the systematic approach, the culture of career choice and 4K skills were considered as a holistic pedagogical system consisting of interrelated elements. The competency-based approach was aimed at the formation of general and transversal competencies necessary for professional activity in students. While the person-oriented approach assumes the consideration of the individual characteristics, interests and needs of students, the activity-oriented approach ensures their development in the process of practical activity.

The study used a set of theoretical and empirical methods. As theoretical methods, the methods of analysis of scientific literature, comparison, generalization and modeling were used to clarify the content, structure and interrelationship of the culture of career choice and 4K skills. Based on the modeling method, a pedagogical model integrated with 4K skills was developed.

Main part. The formation of a culture of career choice among young people is one of the priority areas of the modern education system. This process is characterized by a person's harmonious understanding of his interests, abilities and socio-economic needs and making a conscious professional decision. From this point of view, the culture of career choice is manifested as a multi-component structure, which includes motivational, cognitive, active and reflexive components. The effective development of these components is closely related to the formation of modern competencies in students, in particular 4K skills.

4K skills — critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration — serve as an important factor in students' professional self-awareness and planning their future activities. Critical thinking allows students to analyze various professions, assess their advantages and disadvantages, and make a conscious choice. Creativity helps students demonstrate their abilities in new directions and expand their professional opportunities through innovative thinking. Communicativeness provides effective communication in a professional environment, clear expression of one's thoughts, and mutual understanding with others. Collaboration forms the skills of teamwork, development of social cooperation, and joint

action towards a common goal. As part of the research, a pedagogical model was developed aimed at the integrated development of these skills. This model consists of the following main components: target (general goal aimed at forming a culture of choosing a profession), content (educational materials enriched with 4K skills), technological (interactive methods, project-based learning, problem situations), and outcome (level of development of students' professional competencies). The main feature of this model is that in it 4K skills are formed not separately, but in harmony with each other, as a single pedagogical system.

Interactive methods were widely used in the process of implementing the model in practice. In particular, activities based on "case studies", "brainstorming", project activities, role-playing games and problem situations ensured the active participation of students. For example, students were presented with various professional situations and were taught to analyze these situations, develop alternative solutions and justify their opinions through group discussion. This not only developed their critical thinking, but also their communicative and collaborative skills.

The results of the pilot study showed that the use of an integrative pedagogical model based on 4K skills significantly increased the level of professional orientation of students. In particular, students in the experimental group developed a conscious approach to choosing a profession, the ability to analyze their interests and abilities, and independent decision-making skills. Statistical analysis revealed significant differences between the experimental and control groups, which confirms the effectiveness of the developed model.

It was also noted during the study that students' motivation for the process of choosing a profession increased, and their future plans were formed more clearly and based on their knowledge. This once again confirms the important role of 4K skills in the process of professional self-awareness. At the same time, the level of use of innovative methods in the pedagogical activities of teachers also increased significantly.

In general, the results of the study showed that the integrative pedagogical model based on 4K skills is an effective tool in forming a culture of choosing a profession among young people. The widespread introduction of this model into the educational process will serve to ensure not only the professional competencies of students, but also their personal development.

Conclusions and suggestions. The results of this study showed that the formation of a culture of career choice in young people is a multifaceted pedagogical process that requires a comprehensive approach in the modern education system. During the study, the essence of the culture of career choice was clarified and it was substantiated that it is a systematic structure consisting of motivational, cognitive, active and reflexive components. Also, the manifestation of 4K skills (critical thinking, creativity, communication and collaboration) as an important structural element of this process was scientifically substantiated.

The developed integrative pedagogical model based on 4K skills was confirmed through experimental work as an effective tool for developing students' competencies in conscious career choice, professional self-awareness and independent decision-making. In particular, as a result of the implementation of the model, it was found that the students' professional orientation, critical analysis skills, creative approach, and participation in collective activities significantly increased. This once again confirms the integrative importance of 4K skills in forming a culture of career choice.

Based on the results of the study, the following scientific and practical proposals were developed:

1. It is advisable to systematically introduce an integrative pedagogical model based on 4K skills in organizing career guidance in the educational process.
2. It is necessary to widely use interactive methods (project-based learning, problem situations, role-playing games) in developing students' professional orientation.
3. It is necessary to organize special training and seminars aimed at improving the professional competencies of school psychologists and teachers in career guidance.
4. It is necessary to improve diagnostic methods aimed at identifying the individual characteristics, interests, and abilities of students in the process of career choice.
5. It is necessary to ensure that students are introduced to the real professional environment by strengthening cooperation between educational institutions, parents and labor market entities.
6. It is recommended to increase the efficiency of the career guidance process through the use of digital educational resources and modern information technologies.

In general, the results of this study enrich the scientific and methodological foundations of the formation of a career choice culture in the education system and are of great importance in the implementation of innovative approaches based on 4K skills.

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